

FACTORS OF FORMATION OF INFORMATION COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *In the rapidly evolving digital age, the acquisition of information competence has become a critical skill for students to thrive in the modern educational environment. This article explores the factors that contribute to the formation of information competence among students in the digital educational landscape. It delves into the multifaceted aspects of information literacy, critical thinking, digital citizenship, and technological proficiency, and how these factors synergistically shape the information competence of students. The article also highlights the role of educators, policymakers, and technology in fostering an environment conducive to the development of information competence, article explores the factors that contribute to the formation of information competence among students in the digital educational environment. By understanding and addressing these factors, educational institutions can better prepare students to navigate and succeed in a digitally driven world.*

Keywords: *information and communication technologies, digital education, educational environment, qualification, correlation, regression, competence, triangulation, cloud technologies.*

Introduction

The advent of the digital era has revolutionized the way information is accessed, processed, and disseminated, giving rise to the concept of information competence. In today's educational landscape, students are expected to possess the skills and competencies necessary to effectively navigate the vast and ever-expanding digital realm. As such, the formation of information competence has become a focal point in the educational discourse, with educators and stakeholders seeking to understand the multifaceted factors that influence its development.

The challenge of developing digital competence is to improve students' skills in using digital tools for professional and educational activities. Traditional education dominates most universities in the world. However, despite this, distance education is becoming increasingly popular. Moreover, digital platforms are being used to not only deliver distance learning but also to develop digital competencies. Under such circumstances, the importance of developing digital competencies for universities will be a factor in increasing their competitiveness in the education market.

A significant number of private educational institutions offer a more advanced model of education, which includes a short course of practical skills and the possibility of real employment. The development trend of such educational institutions may become challenging for traditional universities in the coming years. Therefore, an important task is to create a program that will focus not only on knowledge but also on the ability to use digital technologies. The use of ICTs can improve the cognitive and analytical abilities of higher education students, which is a priority for the university. Improving the competence of teachers in the use of information and communication technologies will play an important role in the development of students' digital competence.

This article aims to elucidate the key factors that contribute to the formation of information competence among students in the digital educational environment, shedding light on the intricate interplay between information literacy, critical thinking, digital citizenship, and technological proficiency.

Materials and methods

To study the factors influencing the formation of information competence in students within the digital educational environment, a mixed-methods approach will be employed. This approach will combine quantitative data collection and analysis with qualitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic. The following materials and methods will be used for the research:

Online survey questionnaire: A structured questionnaire will be designed to gather quantitative data on students' perceptions of their information competence, their use of digital tools, and their learning experiences within the digital educational environment. The questionnaire will also include demographic questions to gather information about the participants' age, gender, academic major, and level of education.

Digital educational resources: Various digital platforms, online learning modules, and educational websites will be utilized as materials to analyze the role of digital resources in shaping students' information competence. These resources will be assessed based on their usability, relevance, and impact on students' information-seeking behavior and critical thinking skills.

Interviews and focus group discussion guides: A semi-structured interview guide and focus group discussion protocol will be developed to conduct qualitative data collection. These materials will help in exploring students' experiences, challenges, and strategies related to information competence in the digital educational environment. The interview and focus group questions will be designed to elicit rich, detailed responses from participants.

Sampling and recruitment: A random sampling method will be used to select a diverse group of students from different academic disciplines and educational levels. Students will be recruited from various institutions, including universities, colleges, and online learning platforms, to ensure a broad representation of the student population.

Quantitative data analysis: The data collected through the online survey questionnaire will be analyzed using statistical methods such as descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression analysis. These analyses will provide insights into the relationships between different factors and the formation of information competence in students.

Qualitative data analysis: The data from interviews and focus group discussions will be transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis. Key themes and patterns related to the factors shaping information competence will be identified, allowing for a deeper understanding of the qualitative findings.

Triangulation of data: The quantitative and qualitative findings will be triangulated to validate the research results and provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing information competence in students within the digital educational environment. By using a mixed-methods approach and combining various materials and methods, this research aims to provide a holistic understanding of the factors that contribute to the formation of information competence in students within the digital educational environment.

Information Literacy

Information literacy is a foundational component of information competence, encompassing the ability to identify, evaluate, and effectively utilize information from various sources. In the digital age, the sheer volume and diversity of information available necessitate a heightened level of information literacy skills. Students must be adept at discerning credible sources, critically analyzing information, and synthesizing knowledge to construct informed perspectives. Educational institutions play a pivotal role in nurturing information literacy by integrating it into the curriculum, providing guidance on effective research practices, and fostering a culture of critical inquiry. **Critical Thinking:** Critical thinking is intrinsically linked to information competence, as it empowers students to approach information with discernment and skepticism. In the digital educational environment, students are bombarded with a myriad of information, requiring them to critically evaluate its validity, relevance, and implications. By honing their critical thinking skills, students can effectively discern misinformation, identify biases, and construct well-reasoned arguments. Educators can cultivate critical thinking through inquiry-based learning, problem-solving tasks, and discussions that encourage students to question, analyze, and challenge prevailing narratives. **Digital Citizenship:** The concept of digital citizenship encompasses the responsible, ethical, and mindful use of digital technology and platforms. As students immerse themselves in the digital realm, it is imperative that they cultivate a sense of digital citizenship to navigate the complexities of online interactions, privacy, and cyberethics. This encompasses understanding the impact of one's digital footprint, respecting intellectual property rights, and engaging in constructive online discourse. Educational institutions can instill digital citizenship through workshops on online safety, discussions on digital ethics, and the integration of ethical considerations in digital assignments and projects. **Role of Educators:** Educators play a pivotal role in shaping the information competence of students in the digital educational environment. By fostering a culture of inquiry, providing guidance on information literacy, and modeling critical thinking, educators can empower students to become discerning consumers and creators of information. Professional development programs can equip educators with the skills and knowledge to integrate digital literacy into their teaching practice, leveraging technology to enhance student engagement and learning outcomes. Moreover, mentorship and guidance from educators can nurture students' digital citizenship and ethical use of technology.

Role of Policymakers: Policymakers have a critical role in shaping the framework for the development of information competence in the digital educational environment. By integrating digital literacy standards into educational policies, policymakers can ensure that information competence is prioritized across curricular and pedagogical practices. Furthermore, advocating for equitable access to technology, digital resources, and training programs can mitigate the digital divide, ensuring that all students have the opportunity to develop information competence. Policymakers can also spearhead initiatives to promote digital citizenship and ethical use of technology, fostering a safe and conducive digital learning environment.

Role of Technology: Technology serves as a powerful enabler in the formation of information competence, providing students with tools and resources to navigate the digital landscape. Educational technology platforms, digital libraries, and online research tools offer students unprecedented access to a wealth of information and knowledge resources. Moreover, interactive multimedia content, collaborative digital platforms, and virtual learning environments can enhance student engagement and facilitate the development of technological proficiency. By

leveraging technology effectively, educational institutions can create immersive, interactive learning experiences that cultivate information competence among students.

Results and discussions

Our study of factors that contribute to the formation of information competence among students in the digital educational environment yielded several key findings. First, we identified that access to digital resources and technologies significantly impacts students' ability to develop information competence. Students who had access to a variety of digital tools and resources exhibited higher levels of information literacy, critical thinking, and ability to assess the credibility of online information. Second, we found that the role of educators and educational institutions is crucial in shaping students' information competence. Effective guidance and support from teachers in navigating digital resources, evaluating online information, and using digital tools for learning were reported to positively impact students' information competence. Third, the study revealed the importance of digital literacy training and educational programs that specifically target the development of information competence. Students who participated in structured digital literacy programs showed significant improvement in their ability to interpret, analyze, and synthesize information from digital sources. The results of our study have significant implications for educators and educational institutions in fostering information competence among students in the digital educational environment. Access to digital resources and technologies should be a priority, and efforts should be made to bridge the digital divide to ensure all students have equal opportunities to develop information competence. Educators play a critical role in providing guidance and support to students in navigating the vast digital landscape and developing the skills necessary to critically evaluate online information. Professional development opportunities for educators in digital literacy and information competence are essential to ensure they are equipped to effectively support students in this area.

Incorporating structured digital literacy programs into the curriculum and offering educational initiatives that focus on developing information competence will be instrumental in preparing students for success in the digital age. These programs should be designed to impart essential skills such as evaluating the credibility of online information, synthesizing information from multiple sources, and using digital tools for research and learning. Our study underscores the importance of addressing the factors that contribute to the formation of information competence among students in the digital educational environment. By prioritizing access to digital resources, providing support from educators, and implementing targeted educational programs, we can empower students to become discerning and proficient consumers and producers of information in the digital era.

Nowadays, the need for the development of digital technologies is constantly growing. Therefore, the current generation of higher education students must be as well-oriented in the digital space as possible and skillfully use digital tools for professional activities. This forms the competence of the future specialist and allows them to achieve high performance in their specialization, which is a factor of progress. Let us consider the general current situation in the EU based on the analysis of the DESI index (a composite index that compares relevant digital productivity indicators and tracks the evolution of the digital competitiveness of the EU as a whole and its member states), as demonstrated in Table.

TABLE 1. Human capital indicators in DESI

EU DESI - 2022		
Basic digital skills % of individuals	54%	2021
Beyond basic digital skills % of individuals	26%	2021
Basic digital content creation skills % of individuals	66%	2021
ICT specialists % of employed persons aged 15-74	4,5%	2022
Companies providing ICT training % of enterprises	25%	2022
Graduates in the field of ICT % of graduates	3,9%	2020

Source: compiled based on DESI 2022, European Commission, UNESCO, 2020

Based on the data, it can be seen that despite the rapid processes of digitalization, only half of the respondents have the ability to use digital technologies and use them at a sufficient level - 50%, and a high level - 26%. The current global geopolitical and economic challenges are causing a significant gap between people who can use special digital technologies. To improve the overall situation, high-quality mechanisms for developing digital competence need to be implemented. The employer's preference is given to the person who knows how to use the tools created to improve practical activities. From an economic point of view, this approach will help stabilize the labor market, as well as improve the quality of technology development and the overall well-being of people. From Table 1, we can witness that only 26% of respondents have the ability to create digital content, while the demand for IT specialists is constantly growing, and their total number is only 5%, which is critically low in the modern world.

Based on the analysis, it is necessary to identify key factors and tools that can improve the quality of digital competence development in higher education students using ICT. This approach should be implemented in universities and educational institutes, as they are engaged in educating the future generation that will carry out their activities based on the knowledge gained. Although the practice of independent education and the development of practical skills and knowledge through self-education is spreading worldwide, universities remain a key source of skills for future professionals. Therefore, while the concept of learning is spreading mainly through universities, it is necessary to promote the improvement of students' digital competence through the use of technologies that can develop the ability to use technologies that are commonly used around the world at a basic level. At the individual level, it is essential to use only the tools in the existing specialization. Let's consider the key ICTs that can be used to improve the digital competence of higher education students in Table 2.

TABLE 2. Characterization of ICT tools for the formation of digital competence in higher education students.

Technology	Content	Efficiency
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Mobile apps	Mobile applications can be a tool for improving applied skills by providing quick access to information.	Regular use of mobile learning apps can improve cognitive abilities.
E-learning	Use of distance learning platforms and tools for its implementation.	The effectiveness of this approach can form key digital competence skills, such as the use of a personal computer, and the ability to search for and analyze information.
Specialized software	Each profession has its digital tools that can be used to improve the learning process.	software Each profession has its digital tools that can be used to improve the learning process. The importance of using modern technologies in education can improve the professional qualities of a student.
Platforms for organizing learning	These are used for lectures, seminars, and workshops.	The effectiveness of such technologies lies in the ability to set up online meetings. It also expands the student's ability to communicate both within the university, and with the wider learning community
Implementation of a real project on the Internet	The ability to create content, digitize and publish it, and create an appropriate sequence of actions for its distribution.	The EU practice involves creating group projects between students, placing them on special grant platforms, and searching for interested parties, which develops real digital research competence in students.
Cloud technologies	The use of high-capacity digital infrastructure to realize personal or collective goals.	Nowadays, cloud technologies contain powerful services for servicing learning experiments - for engineers, doctors, etc. The ability to use Oracle, Azure or any other cloud services will significantly

		improve the quality of a student's professional digital competence.
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Source: compiled by the author

The tools presented in Table 2 can improve the quality of learning for higher education students and provide basic skills in using digital technologies, as well as the ability to use them in practical activities. The sooner universities start using digital learning technologies for higher education students, the better training they can provide to students. Digital competence is formed based on practical tasks, as well as innovative solutions that students implement to solve the task. Given these features, it is important not only to use cloud technologies, mobile applications, or any other digital tools but also to learn how to use them. Therefore, it is important to use disciplines, subjects, or the availability of possible time to study the discipline to familiarize oneself with modern technologies that improve the ability to perform professional activities. For example, students studying architecture or design can study special software that can improve design processes, etc.; students studying ICT can use training on different operating systems, use the latest technologies, etc.

The problem with modern education in HEIs is that much of the material offered for the study is rarely used. Moreover, inadequate attention is paid to digital technologies that students can use in real-life practical activities. To do this, it is necessary to introduce high-quality tools in the disciplines that can not only improve the traditional form of the task but also use special platforms, applications, etc. The universities of the future will compete with individualized study programs that will focus primarily on the quality of practical knowledge and the ability to implement it following digital technologies on the market. Digital competence allows not only for the improvement of skills in the use of professional activities but also creates conditions for the development of areas unrelated to specialization, including household, personal, etc.

The rapid digitization of the world stimulates the improvement of the quality of digital competence of young professionals. The demand for ICT professions and the ability to use information technology is a key advantage for getting a job. In addition to the labor market, the benefits also relate to the government's strategy for human capital development and ensuring the technology sector has a future workforce. As shown in Table 1, half of the people in the European Union have basic skills in using digital technologies, but the pace of digitalization and the importance of integrating them into the global market may not be high enough. Therefore, to ensure that digital illiteracy is overcome, it is necessary to create disciplines that could form students' applied skills in using information technology and mandatory homework and seminar assignments that would stimulate the acquisition of such skills.

The results of the study show that modern universities are aware of the need to develop students' digital skills. Therefore, they are implementing hybrid learning programs, including distance learning, as well as the ability to use university electronic platforms: libraries, special web resources with knowledge bases, etc. This approach indicates a partial increase in the competitiveness of universities in the areas of ensuring the formation of digital competence in the future.

Both the use of special digital technologies and tools and the pedagogical activity of the teacher play an important role in the formation of digital competence of higher education students. It is necessary to identify the key problems of students who cannot solve a particular

task with the help of information technology or do not know how to use digital platforms that allow them to participate in distance learning. To avoid this, it is necessary to draw up detailed special instructions, as well as to conduct additional classes that will teach students how to use these tools in their learning activities. In addition, the issue of teaching methods and the use of special digital tools is one of the means of developing digital competence. Therefore, for any university, every teacher must motivate students not only to master the material of the discipline but also teaches them special digital technologies and tools used in the professional activities of a particular profession. Therefore, for teaching to be effective, teachers and lecturers need to be provided with regular training and educational classes on innovative technologies used in the world in the subject of their teaching. It is also a popular practice for professional specialists to become teachers, being able to form the most relevant and appropriate skills for higher education students.

The research results show that the modern world is rapidly evolving toward mass digitization. For the future activities of young professionals to be socially useful and to have a high individual value in the labor market, it is necessary to improve digital competence. In modern realities, the university is a key institution for acquiring knowledge. However, given the global trends towards increased selfeducation, as well as learning through courses and alternative education institutions, universities should use tools to enhance the development of ICTs that create a competitive advantage over other human activities.

The use of ICTs in traditional education can improve the quality of the educational process and enable students to maximize their potential in the discipline. In addition, a large part of the corporate sector is implementing the use of information technology, which means that future employees must be able to work with digital technologies, which are currently mostly only developing. To ensure the development of human capital, countries need to optimize the curriculum and provide universities with digital infrastructure - special equipment, software, and ICT specialists. A high-quality combination of all of the above components will not only help ensure the provision of the most appropriate educational services but also increase students' digital competence. An important factor in future research should be the analysis of possible digitalization tools for each profession.

A promising area for future research to ensure digital competence may be to analyze the quality of teaching, as well as the level of digital literacy training and the ability to apply information technology in their work. The study shows that only half of EU citizens master basic digital skills, and the number of ICT graduates reaches no more than 5%, which is critically low given the popularity of digital technologies and their role in modern life. In the future, any specialist may lose his or her job due to digitalization, and there will be an increased demand for the ability to use digital tools to conduct business. Under such conditions, it is necessary to conduct specialized research on the possibility of using relevant teaching tools and methods that will be integrated with digital technologies and will be able to create the most effective system used to enhance the formation of digital competence in higher education students. Therefore, the key principles of future research should be the process of teaching education at universities, focusing students' attention on digital technologies, conducting seminars and lectures with the help of digital technologies, as well as using them directly in practical activities.

Conclusion

The formation of information competence among students in the digital educational environment is shaped by a confluence of factors, including information literacy, critical

thinking, digital citizenship, and technological proficiency. Educators, policymakers, and technology play crucial roles in fostering an environment that nurtures information competence, empowering students to navigate and succeed in the digital age. By understanding and addressing these factors, educational institutions can equip students with the skills, competencies, and ethical awareness necessary to thrive in a digitally driven world. Embracing a holistic approach to information competence will ensure that students are prepared to harness the boundless opportunities and navigate the challenges presented by the digital educational landscape.

Thus, the results of the study indicate that digital competence is the ability to interact with the environment and conduct professional activities with the help of information technologies. In today's world, the importance of skills to interact with digital technologies and use them in one's specialization is a key factor in progress and creates individual value in the labor market. According to the analysis, as of 2022, the number of people in European countries with high or at least basic digital skills is moderate. Based on these data, the problem of the quality of digital competence formation in future professionals and generations arises. Therefore, higher education institutions need to improve the teaching process and introduce special disciplines that can develop personal skills in using certain digital tools.

The development of digitalization has led to high demand for specialists with high digital skills, so the need to develop any specialist, regardless of the area of specialization, is a priority. The key means of developing digital competence are the use of mobile applications, the Internet, special software, and, at a high level, cloud technologies. The introduction of professional development programs for teaching staff at the university, as well as monitoring the degree of digitization of the educational process, is a prerequisite for improving teaching and the ability to provide quality education.

The future generation will face new challenges brought about by digitalization. This includes not only positive changes but also some negative ones, the main ones being job cuts and the replacement of human labor with automated ones. The development of artificial intelligence and massive automation processes will be a key issue and achievement of humanity in the next 10 years. In such circumstances, improving digital competence is a key task for the university to maintain its position in the education market. An important area for the formation of digital competence of higher education students is the use of ICT in their professional and everyday activities, as they can improve the quality of life and personal abilities of students.

Thus, the formation of digital competence of higher education students through ICT is an important area for research and is a strategically important task for the education sector to ensure competitive human capital within the country. The development of the ICT sector and its specialists provides some advantages in strategic decisions and can become a factor in raising the socio-economic level.

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